

STUDIES ON THE DEPENDENCE OF OPTICAL ACTIVITY ON CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION. PART XLIX. THE ROTATORY DISPERSION OF *o*-, *m*-, *p*-METHOXY- AND ETHOXY-PHENYLIMINO-*d*-CAMPHORS AND *p*-SULPHONAMIDO-, *o*- AND *p*-METHOXYPHENYLAMINO-*d*-CAMPHORS

BY BAWA KARTAR SINGH AND BHUPENDRA SAHAI SAXENA

The rotatory dispersion of *o*-, *m*-, *p*-methoxy- and ethoxy-phenylimino-*d*-camphors and *p*-sulphonamido-, *o*- and *p*-methoxyphenylamino-*d*-camphors has been studied in seven solvents. It is found to be 'simple' as it can be expressed by 'one-term' Drude's equation. The values of the 'characteristic' wave-lengths (λ_0 's) vary from about 3510 Å to 4240 Å for the arylimino compounds, whereas they are considerably less, being about 1850 to 3100 Å for the corresponding arylamino compounds.

The effect of position isomerism and the influence of solvents on rotatory power have been studied. The significant effect of conjugated double bonds on rotatory power has also been discussed.

In the present investigation, we have determined the rotatory power of *o*-, *m*-, *p*-methoxy- and ethoxy-phenylimino-*d*-camphors and *p*-sulphonamido-, *o*- and *p*-methoxyphenylamino-*d*-camphors in seven solvents.

Whereas the rotatory dispersion of the colorless arylamino compounds has been recorded for thirteen wave-lengths (6708 to 4358 Å) in the visible region of the spectrum, it is given for only eight lines (6708 to 5209 Å) in the case of coloured, arylimino compounds.

Nature of the Rotatory Dispersion

The compounds described here exhibit 'simple' rotatory dispersion in all the solvents as their rotatory power can be expressed by Drude's *one-term* equation,

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda} = \frac{K}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$$

where 'K' is the rotation constant and λ_0^2 , the dispersion constant.

The values of λ_0 's, the 'characteristic' wave-lengths, vary from 3513 to 4239 Å for the yellow-coloured arylimino compounds, whereas those for the colorless arylamino compounds are considerably less, being 1847 to 3095 Å, showing that the rotations of these arylamino compounds are controlled by the low frequency characteristic of the 'keto' group, pertaining to the selective absorption band (λ_{max} 2880) of camphor (Lowry and French, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 128, 1923) and sometimes by the high frequency corresponding to the general absorption of the saturated molecules (indicated by italicized figure of values of λ_0 's in Tables V, VI and VII).

While the absorption maxima (λ_{max}) of the arylamino compounds (this issue, p. 227) substantially support the 'characteristic' wave-lengths (λ_0 's), derived from Drude's equation, the high values of the λ_0 's of the arylimino compounds, specially $\lambda_0 = 4000$ Å to $\lambda_0 = 4239$ Å, do not support the absorption spectra data which give two λ_{max} at about 270 and 350 $m\mu$ for these compounds.

An explanation of this discrepancy will be given under the ultraviolet absorption spectra of these compounds.

TABLE A

Molecular rotatory power $[M]_{5481}^{25}$ in different solvents.

Compounds.	MeOH ₄ (31.2)	EtOH ₄ (45.8)	Acetone ₄ (21.5)	Pyridine ₄ (12.4)	EtOAc ₄ (6.11)	CHCl ₃ ₄ (5.4)	Benzene ₄ (2.26)
1. $*R=N-$	672.08	674.79	661.24	742.54	639.56	750.67	712.73
2. $RH-NH-$	226.59	241.61	274.37	214.31	289.02	324.87	248.43
3. $R=N-$	1940.4	1986.4	1924.1	2238.5	2010.8	2127.4	2441.2
4. $R=N-$	3902.4	4092.0	3891.6	4373.9	3945.3	4363.0	4390.2
5. $RH-NH-$	230.69	245.70	256.62	144.69	285.29	309.86	296.21
6. $R=N-$	1445.8	1559.4	1628.8	1646.7	...	1710.4	...
7. $RH-NH-$	301.07	304.29	299.46	170.66	354.2	389.62	...
8. $R=N-$	612.75	621.30	652.65	715.35	561.20	703.95	745.7
9. $R=N-$	1952.3	1963.7	2017.8	2109.0	2034.9	2054.5	2114.7
10. $R=N-$	4172.4	4195.2	4106.9	4639.8	4126.8	4611.3	4619.9
11. $R=N-$	1929.9	2032.4	1966.1	2193.8	...	2100.3	2234.6

*R represents C_6H_5

Figures in parenthesis indicate the dielectric constants of pure solvents.

† These values of the molecular rotation are calculated from the specific rotation values of this compound given by Singh and Manhas, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 30A, 87.

** These values are calculated from the specific rotation of this compound by Singh and Singh, *this Journal*, 1951, 28, 229.

Position Isomerism and Rotatory Power

The rotatory powers of methoxyphenylimino- and ethoxyphenylimino *d*-camphors do not obey Cohen's rule (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1739). The order of the rotatory power, $[\alpha]_{5461}^{25}$, of these compounds in different solvents is $o < m < un < p$. These compounds therefore also do not obey Frankland's 'lever-arm' hypothesis (*ibid.*, 1896, 69, 1309).

The rotatory powers of the methoxy compounds are found to be always higher than those of the corresponding ethoxy compounds. Some departure from this generalisation is, however, to be noted in the *para* isomers where the rotatory power of the ethoxy compound exceeds that of the methoxy derivative for shorter wavelengths in some of the solvents (Tables III, IV and X).

Influence of Solvents on Rotatory Power

With the exception of the behaviour of acetone and pyridine in several cases, it is found that generally the rotatory power increases as the dielectric constant of the solvents decreases (Table A).

Effect of Conjugated Double Bonds on Rotatory Power

A study of Table A reveals that there is a big fall in the values of molecular rotatory power, $[M]_{5461}^{25}$, as we pass from the arylimino- to the corresponding arylamino-*d*-camphors. This remarkable depression in the molecular rotatory power must be correlated with the reduction of the imino group $>C=N-$ to the amino group $>CH-NH-$, *i.e.*, with the break in the conjugation of the double bonds of the carbonyl-azethenoid phenyl groups of the arylimino compounds at the dotted line:

The depression in the rotatory power is remarkable in the case of the *p*-methoxyphenylimino-*d*-camphor (Table A).

This depression in the molecular rotatory power is also accompanied by a marked decrease in the value of the 'characteristic' wave-length from a range of 3513-4239 Å to 1847-3095 Å (Tables I to VII).

TABLE I
o-Methoxyphenylimino-*d*-camphor (m.p. 120°).

Solvents:	MeOH (31.5)*	EtOH (25.8)	Acetone (21.5)	Pyridine (12.4)	Et acetate (6.11)	CHCl ₃ (5.2)	Benzene (2.28)
Conc: (g./100 c.c.):	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.2500	0.2500	0.5000	0.5000
Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{88}{[\alpha]} \\ \lambda \end{array} \right. =$	$\frac{42.065}{\lambda^3 - 0.1289}$	$\frac{39.988}{\lambda^3 - 0.1376}$	$\frac{38.993}{\lambda^3 - 0.1383}$	$\frac{42.20}{\lambda^3 - 0.1442}$	$\frac{39.67}{\lambda^3 - 0.1301}$	$\frac{45.649}{\lambda^3 - 0.133}$	$\frac{45.723}{\lambda^3 - 0.1234}$
$\lambda_0 (\text{\AA}) =$	3591	3710	3720	3798	3677	3647	3513
Lines:	0. c. 0. c. 0. c.	0. c. 0. c. 0. c.	0. c. 0. c. 0. c.	0. c. 0. c. 0. c.	0. c. 0. c. 0. c.	0. c. 0. c. 0. c.	0. c. 0. c. 0. c.
6708	131.0	128.0	125.0	138.0	124.0	144.0	140.0
6838	148.0	144.0	140.0	156.0	140.0	162.0	156.0
6104	172.0	170.0	166.0	184.0	164.0	190.0	184.0
5893	193.0	190.0	186.0	208.0	182.0	213.0	204.0
5780	205.0	204.0	199.0	222.0	196.0	226.0	217.0
5468	247.0	247.0	243.0	274.0	234.0	274.0	266.0
5461	248.0	249.0	244.0	274.0	236.0	277.0	263.0
5299	296.0	295.40	291.0	...	282.0	...	...

* Figures in parentheses are the values of the dielectric constants of the solvents.

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TABLE II
m-Methoxyphenyltinio-d-camphor (m.p. 78.5°).

Solvents:	MeOH	EtOH	Acetone	Pyridine	Et acetate	CHCl ₃	Benzene
Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	c. 5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000
Calc.	$\frac{99.95}{\lambda^3 - 0.1586}$	$\frac{102.8}{\lambda^3 - 0.1579}$	$\frac{100.74}{\lambda^3 - 0.1563}$	$\frac{108.94}{\lambda^3 - 0.1663}$	$\frac{101.13}{\lambda^3 - 0.1619}$	$\frac{108.06}{\lambda^3 - 0.1594}$	$\frac{109.18}{\lambda^3 - 0.1664}$
Lines.	$\lambda_0(\text{Å}) =$ 3983	3975	3953	4078	4024	3993	4079
6708	343.0	352.0	343.0	384.0	351.0	375.0	385.0
6438	391.0	400.0	389.0	440.0	401.0	428.0	441.0
6104	468.0	478.0	465.0	527.0	480.0	510.0	529.0
5803	529.0	545.0	529.0	611.0	545.0	581.0	603.0
5780	571.0	585.0	567.0	650.0	589.0	625.0	651.0
5468	711.0	728.0	705.0	821.0	737.0	780.0	823.0
5461	716.0	733.0	710.0	826.0	741.0	785.0	827.0
5209	885.0	908.0	876.0	...	923.0	972.0	1040.8

TABLE IV
p-Methoxyphenylimino-d-camphor (β -form, m.p. 120°).

Solvents: Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	MeOH	EtOH	Acetone	Pyridine	Et acetate	CHCl ₃	Benzene
	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500
Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha]_{D}^{25} \\ \lambda \end{array} \right. =$	$\frac{188.92}{\lambda^2 - 0.1672}$	$\frac{195.99}{\lambda^2 - 0.1684}$	$\frac{186.45}{\lambda^2 - 0.1684}$	$\frac{193.32}{\lambda^2 - 0.1747}$	$\frac{189.43}{\lambda^2 - 0.1681}$	$\frac{199.66}{\lambda^2 - 0.1742}$	$\frac{196.73}{\lambda^2 - 0.1768}$
Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda_0 \\ \lambda_1 \end{array} \right. =$	4088	4104	4104	4186	4100	4174	4206
Lines.	o. c. o.						
67c8	668.0	696.0	662.0	724.0	672.0	724.0	720.0
6438	762.0	794.0	754.0	830.0	770.0	823.0	827.7
6104	920.0	956.0	916.0	1007.7	928.0	1008.0	1005.3
5893	1054.0	1100.0	1042.8	1156.0	1054.0	1154.0	1154.5
5780	1132.0	1184.0	1120.0	1250.0	1136.0	1250.0	1250.7
5468	1438.0	1506.0	1427.6	1606.0	1444.0	1600.0	1609.9
5461	1440.0	1510.0	1436.0	1624.0	1456.0	1610.0	1620.0
5209	1810.0	1910.0	1816.0	2060.0	1811.9	2054.0	2056.2

TABLE V
o-Methoxyphenylamino-*d*-camphor (m.p. 148°).

Lines.	Solvents:						
	MeOH	EtOH	Acetone	Pyridine	Et acetate	Chloroform	Benzene
Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
6708	54.00	54.50	62.00	47.50	63.00	70.50	53.50
6418	56.97	59.87	68.10	52.50	70.00	78.00	60.00
6104	64.25	67.79	77.00	59.49	80.00	88.00	68.14
5893	69.60	73.66	84.00	64.50	86.80	97.07	74.50
5780	72.74	77.12	88.00	68.00	91.05	102.00	78.31
5468	81.74	88.21	100.00	78.50	104.82	118.00	90.67
5461	83.00	88.50	100.50	78.50	105.18	119.00	91.00
5209	92.81	99.50	113.50	88.00	119.02	136.50	101.58
5087	98.24	106.50	119.85	94.00	126.83	145.50	111.50
4800	113.12	122.69	139.00	...	148.00	172.00	131.14
4678	120.55	131.29	149.50	...	160.00	187.00	142.00
4603	125.63	137.23	155.50	...	168.50	199.00	149.00
4358	142.00	144.34	170.50	...	197.50	236.00	177.91

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{21.132}{\lambda^2 - 0.0436}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{21.532}{\lambda^2 - 0.0549}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{24.571}{\lambda^2 - 0.0537}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{18.219}{\lambda^2 - 0.0686}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{24.34}{\lambda^2 - 0.0668}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{25.81}{\lambda^2 - 0.0813}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{29.157}{\lambda^2 - 0.0767}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{2562}{\lambda^2 - 0.0686}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{2585}{\lambda^2 - 0.0668}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{2851}{\lambda^2 - 0.0813}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{2770}{\lambda^2 - 0.0767}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{2318}{\lambda^2 - 0.0537}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{2343}{\lambda^2 - 0.0549}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{24571}{\lambda^2 - 0.0537}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{18219}{\lambda^2 - 0.0686}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{2434}{\lambda^2 - 0.0668}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{2581}{\lambda^2 - 0.0813}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{25} = \frac{29157}{\lambda^2 - 0.0767}$$

TABLE VI

p-Methoxyphenylamino-*d*-camphor (m.p. 101°).

Solvents: Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	MeOH	EtOH	Acetone	Pyridine	Et acetate	CHCl ₃	Benzene
	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
$[\alpha]_D^{25} =$	20.119	20.591	23.726	13.276	22.587	23.508	21.9504
$\frac{[\alpha]_D^{25}}{\lambda}$	$\frac{20.119}{\lambda^2 - 0.1601}$	$\frac{20.591}{\lambda^2 - 0.0694}$	$\frac{23.726}{\lambda^2 - 0.0458}$	$\frac{13.276}{\lambda^2 - 0.0477}$	$\frac{22.587}{\lambda^2 - 0.0811}$	$\frac{23.508}{\lambda^2 - 0.0916}$	$\frac{21.9504}{\lambda^2 - 0.0938}$
Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda_2(\text{Å}) = \\ \lambda_1(\text{Å}) = \end{array} \right.$	$\left. \begin{array}{l} 2452 \\ 0. \end{array} \right\}$	$\left. \begin{array}{l} 2635 \\ 0. \end{array} \right\}$	$\left. \begin{array}{l} 2140 \\ 0. \end{array} \right\}$	$\left. \begin{array}{l} 2184 \\ 0. \end{array} \right\}$	$\left. \begin{array}{l} 2848 \\ 0. \end{array} \right\}$	$\left. \begin{array}{l} 3026 \\ 0. \end{array} \right\}$	$\left. \begin{array}{l} 3095 \\ 0. \end{array} \right\}$
Lines.							
6708	51.5	54.0	58.5	33.0	61.5	65.5	62.0
6438	57.0	59.5	64.5	36.0	68.5	73.0	69.0
6104	64.5	68.0	72.0	41.0	77.5	83.5	79.0
5893	70.0	74.5	78.72	44.5	85.0	91.5	88.0
5780	73.0	77.79	82.29	46.0	89.67	97.0	92.5
5468	84.5	89.5	93.5	52.83	104.0	113.0	108.07
5461	84.5	89.99	94.0	52.99	104.5	113.5	108.5
5209	95.5	101.0	105.0	59.0	119.27	130.5	125.13
5087	100.5	108.77	112.0	63.5	127.74	140.0	134.81
4800	117.5	127.89	128.5	72.66	151.95	168.72	163.15
4678	127.5	137.73	136.5	...	164.0	183.3	178.39
4603	133.0	144.59	143.0	...	181.0	195.0	189.31
4358	155.0	170.73	164.5	...	208.0	237.71	234.0

TABLE VII

p-Sulphonamidophenylamino-d-camphor (m.p. 181.5°).

Solvents: Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	MeOH	EtOH	Acetone	Pyridine	Et acetate	CHCl ₃						
	1.0000	1.0000	0.5000	1.0000	0.5000	0.5000						
Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha]_D^{25} \\ \lambda \end{array} \right. =$	$\frac{24.70}{\lambda^2 - 0.0341}$	$\frac{24.164}{\lambda^2 - 0.0425}$	$\frac{22.661}{\lambda^2 - 0.0833}$	$\frac{13.276}{\lambda^2 - 0.0477}$	$\frac{25.261}{\lambda^2 - 0.0686}$	$\frac{26.58}{\lambda^2 - 0.0783}$						
	1847	2062	2310	2184	2618	2798						
Lines.	$\left. \begin{array}{l} 0. \\ c. \end{array} \right\}$											
6708	60.0	59.39	59.0	59.30	58.0	57.13	33.0	33.00	65.0	66.22	72.0	71.50
6438	64.5	64.93	65.0	64.96	62.0	62.74	36.5	36.19	73.0	73.01	78.0	79.02
6104	73.0	73.00	73.0	73.22	71.0	70.99	41.0	40.87	83.0	83.09	90.0	90.34
5893	79.5	78.89	79.5	79.30	78.0	77.10	44.5	44.32	91.0	90.65	99.0	98.82
5780	82.0	82.33	83.0	82.86	80.0	80.71	46.0	46.35	95.0	95.13	104.0	104.00
5468	93.5	93.24	94.0	94.21	92.0	92.24	52.5	52.83	109.0	109.62	120.0	120.40
5461	93.5	93.53	94.5	94.50	93.0	92.54	53.0	52.99	110.0	110.00	121.0	120.9
5209	103.0	104.20	106.5	105.61	103.0	103.94	59.5	59.37	124.5	124.57	138.0	137.0
5087	116.0	109.97	112.0	111.76	110.0	110.16	63.0	62.92	133.0	132.88	145.0	147.3
4800	125.5	125.82	128.0	128.60	127.0	127.62	73.5	72.66	155.0	155.60	174.0	174.3
4678	134.0	133.65	137.0	136.99	137.0	136.91	...	...	168.0	168.07	190.0	189.1
4603	139.0	139.00	141.5	142.72	143.0	143.00	...	...	176.0	176.31	199.0	199.1
4348	159.0	158.43	165.0	163.82	165.0	165.81	...	...	208.0	208.00	238.0	238.0

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TABLE VIII

o-Ethoxyphenylimino-*d*-camphor (m.p. 53°).

Solvents:	MeOH	EtOH	Acetone	Pyridine	Et acetate	CHCl ₃	Benzene
Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000
$\left[\alpha \right]_{589}^{25} =$	$\frac{35.495}{\lambda^2 - 0.1331}$	$\frac{30.192}{\lambda^2 - 0.1597}$	$\frac{36.935}{\lambda^2 - 0.1370}$	$\frac{37.860}{\lambda^2 - 0.1476}$	$\frac{35.218}{\lambda^2 - 0.1464}$	$\frac{34.243}{\lambda^2 - 0.1598}$	$\frac{42.92}{\lambda^2 - 0.1344}$
Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda_0(\text{Å}) = \end{array} \right.$	3648	3996	3702	3843	3826	3997	3666
Lines.	$\left. \begin{array}{l} 0. \\ c. \end{array} \right\}$						
6708	112.0	104.0	118.0	125.0	116.0	119.0	136.0
6438	126.0	118.0	133.0	141.0	132.0	134.0	153.0
6104	148.0	141.0	156.0	168.0	156.0	161.0	180.0
5893	166.0	161.0	175.0	189.0	175.0	183.0	201.0
5780	177.0	173.0	187.0	202.0	188.0	197.0	214.0
5468	214.0	216.0	228.0	249.0	230.0	246.0	260.0
5461	215.0	217.0	229.0	251.0	232.0	247.0	262.0
5209	258.0	270.0	275.0	305.0	283.0	308.0	314.0
5087	281.0	304.0	...	340.0	311.0	346.0	346.0

TABLE IX
m-Ethoxyphenylimino-d-camphor (m.p. 82.5°).

Solvents :	MeOH	EtOH	Acetone	Pyridine	Et acetate	CHCl ₃	Benzene
Conc.-(g./100 c.c.):	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000
$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha]_D^{20} \\ \lambda \end{array} \right. =$	$\frac{96.655}{\lambda^2 - 0.1571}$	$\frac{96.12}{\lambda^2 - 0.1587}$	$\frac{96.506}{\lambda^2 - 0.1619}$	$\frac{103.59}{\lambda^2 - 0.1582}$	$\frac{99.665}{\lambda^2 - 0.1586}$	$\frac{102.01}{\lambda^2 - 0.1594}$	$\frac{106.17}{\lambda^2 - 0.1551}$
Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda_0(\Delta) = \end{array} \right.$	3964	3985	4024	3977	3983	3993	3938
Lines.	$\frac{0}{330.0}$	$\frac{0}{330.0}$	$\frac{0}{335.0}$	$\frac{0}{355.0}$	$\frac{0}{342.0}$	$\frac{0}{351.0}$	$\frac{0}{360.0}$
6703	330.0	330.0	335.0	355.0	342.0	351.0	360.0
6438	375.0	376.0	382.0	404.0	389.0	403.0	409.3
6704	449.0	451.0	460.0	485.0	467.0	479.0	488.4
5893	509.0	510.0	521.0	550.0	528.0	545.0	552.7
5780	546.0	547.0	562.0	589.0	569.0	582.0	594.0
5468	679.0	683.0	704.0	734.0	709.0	731.0	737.8
5461	685.0	689.0	708.0	740.0	714.0	735.0	742.0
5209	845.0	855.0	881.0	912.0	882.0	910.0	915.0
5087	950.0	960.0	999.0	1028.0	993.0	1027.3	1024.8

TABLE X

p-Ethoxyphenylimino-*d*-camphor (m.p. 112°).

Solvents :	MeOH	EtOH	Acetone	Pyridine	Et acetate	CHCl ₃	Benzene
Conc. (g./100 c.c.) :	0.2500	0.2500	0.5000	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.5000
$[\alpha]_D^{25}$	182.56	185.76	182.84	196.816	185.21	195.04	192.57
Calc. $\frac{[\alpha]}{\lambda}$	$\frac{182.56}{\lambda^2 - 0.1734}$	$\frac{185.76}{\lambda^2 - 0.1724}$	$\frac{182.84}{\lambda^2 - 0.1713}$	$\frac{196.816}{\lambda^2 - 0.1774}$	$\frac{185.21}{\lambda^2 - 0.1702}$	$\frac{195.04}{\lambda^2 - 0.1771}$	$\frac{192.57}{\lambda^2 - 0.1796}$
$\lambda_0(\text{Å}) =$	4164	4153	4139	4212	4126	4209	4239
Lines.	o. c.	o. c.	o. c.	o. c.	o. c.	o. c.	o. c.
6708	660.0	667.0	656.0	722.0	662.0	718.6	712.0
6438	758.0	766.0	751.8	832.0	756.0	824.0	820.0
6104	914.0	924.0	907.0	1008.0	918.0	1004.0	996.0
5893	1050.0	1059.0	1040.0	1158.0	1046.0	1152.0	1148.0
5780	1136.0	1146.0	1123.0	1256.0	1130.0	1248.0	1246.0
5468	1452.0	1453.5	1430.0	1620.0	1440.0	1607.4	1612.3
5461	1464.0	1462.8	1441.0	1628.0	1446.9	1618.0	1621.0
5209	1862.0	1864.7	1830.0	1828.4	1831.9	2082.0	2102.0
5087	2144.0	2140.2	2148.0	2145.5	2148.0	2398.0	2451.2

Dimorphic Forms

The *p*-methoxyphenylimino-*d*-camphor exists in two dimorphic forms as described before (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 103). We have found the rotatory dispersion of both the forms to be the same, within limits of experimental error. These forms therefore behave similarly in solution (Tables III and IV).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The compounds studied here were prepared and purified as described earlier (*loc. cit.*). The rotatory dispersion was determined in a 2 dm jacketed polarimeter tube. Water at 35° was kept circulating through the jacket. The observations are recorded in Tables I to X.

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ORGANIC CHEMISTRY RESEARCH SECTION,
THE BENARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
VARANASI.

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